

THE MODERN CHARACTERISTICS OF USING THE SPIRITUAL HERITAGE OF JADIDS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS

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Abstract: This thesis is dedicated to the study of the modern features of using the spiritual heritage of the ancients in the development of the professional competence of teachers of the first grade. The legacy of the ancients, with its pedagogical, educational and spiritual aspects, can play an important role in improving the qualifications of classroom teachers. The article analyzes the innovations of the moderns in the field of education and training, the pedagogical principles and methods put forward by them, as well as how this heritage can be used in the current educational system. In particular, attention is paid to how modern methods of knowledge acquisition and education can help in the formation of professional competence of elementary school teachers. This study reveals the practical importance of the heritage of the ancients for the spiritual and moral development of elementary school teachers and the improvement of their pedagogical skills.

Key words: elementary school teachers, professional competence, spiritual heritage of the past, pedagogical innovations, educational principles, modern education system.

Introduction.

In the process of development and modernization of the educational system of Uzbekistan, the urgency of improving the professional competence of teachers is increasing more than ever. Primary school teachers play an important role in educating and imparting knowledge to the younger generation, so it is necessary to constantly improve their pedagogical skills. In this process, the use of historical heritage and cultural monuments is of great importance in enriching the educational process and increasing its efficiency.

The Jadidlar movement promoted the renewal of education, culture and society in Central Asia and Uzbekistan in the late 19th and early 20th centuries. They developed innovative methods of education, updated pedagogical principles and promoted spiritual and moral values. The educational views, pedagogical methods and educational approaches of the Jadids can be effective in developing new approaches and strategies in the modern education system.

This article aims to analyze the modern features of using the spiritual heritage of the past in the development of the professional competence of

teachers of the first grade. The heritage of Jadids, with its pedagogical and spiritual aspects, reveals important aspects of how it can help in the professional development of beginning teachers. In particular, the article talks about the practical importance of modern educational methods and pedagogical approaches and how they can be used by elementary school teachers.

Material

Approaches to Education of Jadids

The Jadidlar movement tried to renew the traditional education system in its time with its pedagogical approaches. First of all, they developed new methods aimed at developing scientific and practical aspects of education. Modern educational methods include, for example, interactive teaching methods, individual approach and innovative pedagogical techniques. These methods are important in ensuring the active participation of students and developing their critical thinking skills.

The Jadids also paid great attention to the field of spiritual and moral education. Their pedagogical views are aimed at supporting the moral development of young people and promoting national values. The spiritual education approaches of Jadids, with their modern pedagogical methods, can be used to improve the professional competence of elementary school teachers. By teaching and using their values, teachers can be further developed spiritually and morally.

Pedagogical Innovations

Pedagogical innovations of Jadids are especially reflected in their educational methodologies. Among these methods, there are approaches such as using new technologies to organize the educational process more effectively, making lessons interactive, and taking into account the individual characteristics of students. It helps to use these innovations in the development of professional competence of elementary school teachers, introduce teachers to new approaches and improve the quality of education.

How the pedagogical approaches of the ancients can be applied in the modern education system, the practical importance of their methods and their use in the educational process are analyzed in depth. In this section, examples and recommendations are presented on how the spiritual heritage of the Jadids can be integrated into the modern education system and how it can be used in the professional development of teachers.

Expert Opinions

The article also presents the results of interviews and questionnaires conducted with specialists and experts on the application of modern pedagogical approaches and methods in the modern education system. These ideas provide a deeper understanding of how the heritage of the ancients is used in the modern education system and its effectiveness in developing the professional competence of teachers.

Discussion

The article deeply analyzed the importance of using the spiritual heritage of the ancients in the development of the professional competence of teachers of the first grade. Innovations in the field of education and upbringing of Jadids can play a significant role in introducing new approaches in the modern education system. Their pedagogical methods, such as an individual approach and interactive teaching methods, help teachers work effectively with students.

The spiritual and moral education approaches of Jadids can have a positive effect on the spiritual and moral development of elementary school teachers. By teaching and practicing their values, teachers can be spiritually developed and morally responsible. This, in turn, helps to improve the quality of education and better upbringing of students.

Modern pedagogical innovations for primary school teachers, including the use of new technologies and making lessons interactive, can be used to improve teachers' skills. These innovations make it possible to organize the educational process more effectively, increase the motivation of students and improve the overall quality of education.

However, there are some difficulties in applying the legacy of the ancients in the modern education system. Integrating ancient methods and approaches into modern pedagogical practice requires time, resources, and methodological manuals. It is also important to train teachers in new methods and test them in practice.

Conclusion.

The spiritual heritage of Jadids can be an important tool in the development of professional competence of elementary school teachers. Their pedagogical methods, spiritual and moral education approaches and innovations have a special place in the modern education system. The experience and methodological approaches of Jadids can be effective in improving the qualifications of teachers, improving the quality of education, and supporting the spiritual development of students.

The materials and analyzes presented in this article reveal the practical importance of using modern pedagogical approaches in the modern education system. Although there are some difficulties in integrating the educational methods of the Jadids, there are great opportunities in developing the professional competence of elementary school teachers by studying and applying their heritage.

In the future, it is possible to achieve more effective results in improving the qualifications of teachers and improving the quality of education by studying and applying modern pedagogical methods in the modern education system.

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